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Cdyl2 is a driver in human cancer.

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We used computational tools to identify a recurrent role for *Cdyl2* as a bona fide driver in human cancer.

Citations

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2. Okashita, N., Maeda, R. and Tachibana, M., 2023. CDYL reinforces male gonadal sex determination through epigenetically repressing Wnt4 transcription in mice. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(20), p.e2221499120.

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Results

1. GSE150306

MCF7 stably expressing CDYL2
n=3 control vector vs n=3 CDYL2-MCF7

2. GSE150319

MDA-MB-231 depleted of CDYL2
n=3 siLUC vs n=3 siCDYL2